

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF FINNED SINGLE BASIN SOLAR STILL INTEGRATED WITH A PCM BASED HEAT SINK

Md. Mainuddin Sagar^{*1}, Md. Jamil Khan Asif^{*2}, Rafid Faisal^{*3},

Dr. Kazi Afzalur Rahman^{*4}

^{*1,2}Research Scholar, Department Of Mechanical Engineering, Chittagong University Of Engineering & Technology, Chittagong, Bangladesh.

^{*3}Research Scholar, Department Of Electrical And Electronics Engineering, American International University, Bangladesh.

^{*3}Professor, Department Of Mechanical Engineering, Chittagong University Of Engineering & Technology, Chittagong, Bangladesh.

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ABSTRACT

One of the elements which decide the existence of all living things is water. So, every nation is trying to find a more reliable source of water. The main objective of this study is to increase the productivity and production time of a single basin solar still within the same structure. An experimental performance analysis of modified solar still (MSS) and conventional solar still (CSS) will be investigated. The design of MSS includes hollow porous fins on the absorber plate, phase change material (PCM); and paraffin wax in this case beneath the absorber plate. PCM will absorb heat in the daytime and release it at night; which will increase production time. Hopefully, almost free and a good amount of distilled water will be obtained. A comparative result of MSS and CSS will be investigated in the same climate condition.

Keywords: Solar Still, Saline Water, Fin, PCM, Paraffin Wax, Desalination.

I. INTRODUCTION

Solar still is kind of process where the heat absorption and distillation processes occurs within the same structure and solar energy is used directly. Saline or brackish water is stored in a transparent structure where it evaporates due to absorption of solar radiation and then condenses by releasing some energy to the surroundings. Condensed droplets run down and collected as fresh water. Solar still technology mainly used for small scale production. But by developing it now we can see that it's a very efficient and reliable technology for desalination or recycling water and further development can make it more reliable for many countries of those who are still dependent on costly and energy consuming methods.

In search for an easy and reliable method for desalination, found many technologies and many relevant publications on desalination. Common thing is how desperately people are searching for more reliable source of water. All methods can be categorized into two sections, first one phase change process and second one is membrane process. Many researches were performed on solar desalination in those areas that normally use less productive desalination processes. In these cases, we have a great opportunity in hybrid system. Hybrid systems generally have a lower cost compared to similar capacity solar only desalination systems; however, most of the systems have a large capacity around 100m³/day. Hybrid systems can reduce fossil fuel energy usage rate, minimize fuel transportation costs, and provide water that is not weather or season dependent. We can see very few studies have been done on small scale solar assisted hybrid desalination system that leaves a big opportunity for research and development of such systems. Let's see some of the previous works regarding solar still and some opinions from the experts. Kumar et al. [6] in their solar stills system design tried to show various solar stills. They admitted a lot of energy gets wasted in single effect solar still and efficiency is also low. But this kind of system setup cost is very cheap. Rajaseenivasan and Srithar [7] done an experiment on the performance of solar still with circular fins and square fins. They used steel as a fin material and they also discussed about the effect of brackish water height in still performance. They found that keeping the height as low as possible gives the best efficiency. And it was close to 1cm. They also found the productivity is more when they used square fins. The efficiency of square and circular finned stills is 15% and 13% higher than

conventional solar still respectively. Deshmukh et al. [8] done an experiment on a single basin solar stills passive storage material under the basin surface. They used sand and servotherm medium oil as passive storage. They used various height of passive storage and compared them with conventional solar still. They found unsatisfactory result for sand because of its bad conductivity with basin surface. But their result with SM oil was satisfactory because heat transfer was better with basin surface. Velmurugan et al. [9] done an experiment to enhance productivity of single basin solar still using fins. They compared their result with convention solar still and solar still with wick. They saw that fins helps to decrease the preheating time of saline water and it increases the productivity quickly. They found the productivity increases almost 45% when fin is used at the bottom of the still. Feilizadeh et al. [10] done an experiment on the geometry i.e., length, height, width of a single basin solar still. They found that increasing the height of the solar still boundary it decreases the efficiency. As per them the height of the front wall should not exceed 10 cm. Excessive heights create shadow which resist solar radiation entering. The inclination of the glass should be 30°. They concluded that just by selecting proper geometry of a solar still anyone can enhance efficiency without additional cost. Omara et al. [11] done an experiment to increase the surface area of the absorber plate and to increase the heat transfer rate between saline water and absorber. They saw that when finned solar still and corrugated solar still used the efficiency increases by 40% and 21% respectively. They used 1.5mm thick steel sheet to make the still, glass thickness was 3mm and inclination was 30°. And they kept the setup in north direction to receive maximum solar energy. They also analyzed the daily efficiency and estimated cost of 1 l of produced water. They found for finned, corrugated and conventional solar stills are approximately 47.5%–0.041 \$, 41%–0.047 \$ and 35%–0.049 \$ respectively. Selvaraj et al. [12] done a very precise and detailed experiment on the factors affecting the efficiency of a solar still. They researched many things like glass cover thickness, inclination of glass cover, wind effect, fin and corrugated surface, thermal storage material, phase change material etc. They used 3mm, 5mm and 6mm glass and found 15.5% more production in 3mm glass. They saw when wind velocity increases the convection heat transfer between wind and glass increases significantly. And this results in better production rate. When the velocity changes 0 m/s to 10 m/s the efficiency increases by 50%. They preferred galvanized iron or galvanized steel for absorber plate. They experimented in different inclination of the glass cover; among 15°, 25°, 35°, 45° and 55° they found that 35° was giving maximum production. For energy storage material they recommended rubber, gravel, natural rocks, pebbles and quartz. They also investigated about phase change material and found 75% more production overnight. They used paraffin wax as phase change material. Using fins in single basin solar still they found 45% more productivity. Sharshil et al. [13] done a review on factors affecting the production of solar still like weather, operations, design parameters and some enhancement technique like wick, internal and external reflector, internal and external condenser, phase change materials etc. they saw that if we can increase the temperature between glass surface and water it will increase air circulation inside the still which will enhance evaporative and convective heat transfer. They recommended regenerative solar still, still with double glasses and triple basin still for increasing glass cover and water temperature difference. Shalaby et al. [14] done an experiment on single basin integrated with phase change material. They used corrugated plate as absorber. They choose paraffin wax as PCM. As per them paraffin wax is suitable for medium storage, safe, reliable, low melting point and cheap. They found better performance using corrugated surface and PCM with compared to another configuration. They saw PCM stores more energy than sensible storage materials. Their PCM tank was made from galvanized steel. Abu-Arabi et al. [15] examined theoretically the behavior of glass-cooled solar still with PCM integrated to solar collector. They investigated the effect of controllable and uncontrollable parameters on efficiency and production rate. Using both solar collector and phase change material enhanced their productivity. They used various types of phase change material; like paraffin wax, sodium acetate trihydrate, sodium thiosulfate pentahydrate and among these sodium acetate trihydrate was more efficient. Mousa et al. [16] examined empirically the influences of tubes filled with PCM on still yield. They used PCM to analyze the temperature difference throughout the day. Candle wax used as PCM and they measured the production. Production of water was greatly enhanced in the presence of candle wax. Their conclusion was the production of water decrease during day time in the presence of candle wax but increase during night time. El-Maghlany et al. [17] examined the influences of discrete and continuous makeup brackish water on still yield. They showed that continuous feeding of water makes production rate low. And they compared continuous feeding as a solar still penalty. Discrete feeding enhances

the productivity and productivity also increase if we can manage to keep water level nearly 1cm. Srivastava and Agrawal [18] used the porous fins to improve the yield of single slope still. Their experiment was very basic type. They used porous fins to improve production of water. They managed to start early morning and reached higher operating temperature. This experiment was carried out in different month of the year and they got maximum production in the month of May. Vigneswaran et al. [19] conducted the impacts of using multiple phase change material on still yield. Their experiment was in three conditions; conventional solar still, solar still with single phase change material and solar still with multiple phase change material. As expected, they found high production rate in multiple phase change material and the efficiency increases almost 46%. Dumka et al. [20] improved the yield of solar still using sand-filled cotton bags. They used sand filled cotton bags vertically in the basin area to enhance energy storage capacity. They managed to increase the efficiency of the system. They also analyzed the efficiency with different amount of water. They used 40kg and 30kg of water and got 31.31 and 28.96% higher internal efficiency for basin water. Appadurai and Velmurugan [21] connected the finned with a mini solar pond to improve the yield of finned solar still. They made many modified solar stills; like single slope solar still, fin type solar still, mini solar pond, fin type mini solar pond and found maximum production rate in fin type mini solar pond integrated with fin type solar still. Fin type mini solar pond with conventional solar still, fin type single basin solar still and fin type mini solar pond integrated with fin type single basin solar still have increased the production rate, which is found to be around 47%, 45.5% and 50%, respectively. Alaian et al. [22] examined the influences of pin finned wick surface on still behavior. They conducted the experiment in different weather condition and showed that the performance fluctuates with the fluctuation of weather. Their pin finned wick surface managed to improve the still yield by 23%. And efficiency of the system was 55% highest recorded. Rajesh and Tiwari [23] conducted an experiment on the effect of basin water height with the production rate. They have done the experiment on winter season by 24h with different water height in the basin. They used 5cm, 10cm and 15cm water height for passive and active solar distillation. They found condensation of water significantly depends on water height. And got more yield during the off shine hours compared to the day time for 10cm and 15cm. Abdelgaied et al. [24] done an experiment on tubular solar still. They examined three situations of solar still. Conventional solar still, solar still with fin and finned solar still with phase change material. They used two types of fins. For square fin they got 5.52 l/m² per day with 33% improvement. For circular fin they got 6.11 l/m² per day with improvement of 48%. Their final setup result was 7.89 l/m² per day with 90% improvement where they used PCM in hollow circular finned solar still.

By reading those journals and articles we can see solar still efficiency depend on some major elements like sky clearness, ambient temperature, wind velocity, water height in the basin, thermal insulation, leakage control, geometry of the structure etc. Many scientists have already done so many experiments and improvements in solar still technology. We can easily understand why people are more interested in this method; because it is less costly and by improving it can be more productive thus, we can use this method in industrial scale.

There're some issues that could have been added or improved by the researchers. Very few of them showed cost analysis of the system used. Most of them used paraffin wax as PCM. But paraffin wax has some demerits too; like its volume increases when it changes into liquid, another problem is air bubbles inside paraffin wax. Almost no one mentioned these problems. Most importantly none of them talked about brine management. Brine is concentrated saline water and it can easily destroy marine life.

This study follows the investigation of the performance of a finned single basin solar still integrated with phase change material as a heat sink. There will be a comparative result shown after the experiment between conventional and modified solar still.

II. METHODOLOGY

Solar still desalination or recycling of water is fully dependent on solar energy. Conventional solar still has a very poor production rate. If we can add another technology with solar still then its productivity will increase rapidly. As this process doesn't use fossil fuel, we can say it is less harmful process for environment.

2.1 Introduction

There are many designs for solar still desalination. Modification of single basin solar still includes fin on the absorber surface and phase change material beneath the absorber surface. For heat absorption plate galvanized

steel and for fins aluminum is a good choice. For phase change material using paraffin wax or regular wax makes this design more affordable. The design was done in Microsoft word 2010. In previous chapters we have seen background history, many previous works and some of their research gap. In this chapter experimental setup and working method is explained.

2.2 System Flowchart

2.3 Design Of The Solar Still

The setup design in Microsoft word 2010 is shown below. Figure 2.1 shows the modified solar still and figure 2.2 shows conventional solar still.

Fig 2.1: Modified Single Basin Solar Still

Fig 2.2: Conventional Solar Still

If we simply explain the process, saline water is filled inside an air structure which is covered with a transparent glass or plastic cover. When solar radiation hit the absorber surface it absorbs heat and increase the water temperature within it. The hot water then increases the temperature of the air inside still structure and make it unsaturated. Then water evaporates and makes the air saturated. Saturated air circulated within the boundary due to temperature difference between glass cover and water. When water touches the glass cover surface it releases some heat get condensed and we'll collect this water as our experimental product. We'll focus on the rate of production after sunset. Because our main motive is to increase production time and get better productivity.

We're going to use paraffin wax as phase change material. Shalaby et al. [14] experimented the solar still based on PCM and got an improvement in production rate of about 72.7% overnight when paraffin wax was used as PCM. Properties of paraffin wax are shown in table 2.1 [14].

Table 2.1: Properties of Paraffin Wax [14]

Properties	Values
Melting point	56° C
Specific Heat of solid/liquid	2950/2510 J/kg °C
Density of solid/liquid	818/760 kg/m ³
Thermal conductivity of solid/liquid	0.24 W/ m °C
Latent heat of fusion	2.26 × 10 ⁵ J/kg

The height of the PCM storage tank should be around 3cm. And we have to keep a free space on the both side of the tank because as we know paraffin wax expands when it changes its phase. We have to make sure that there's no way of bubble formation. Before filling PCM tank with paraffin wax we have to check it with water if there is any leakage. For fin we're going to use aluminum. Srivastava and Agrawal [18] used porous fin and they got better result in the morning. 1.5cm long, 1cm diameter, 1mm thick hollow porous aluminum tube is better choice for us. The arrangement will be 5×11, 5cm apart from each other in square manner. Just by using fin we can increase 40- 50% productivity.

Fig 2.3: Hollow porous aluminum fin

We have to keep the brackish or saline water height as low as possible. Rajamanickam et al. [26] done an investigation in a double slope solar still where he took various water depths. He used 1 cm, 2.5 cm, 5 cm, 7.5 cm and found a maximum production rate of per day 3.07 l/m² at 1 cm water depth. Continuous feeding is not recommended at all. Maghlany [17] saw that in discrete feeding of water the production increases 0.25 l per day. We need many measuring devices for the experiment. The result of our paper depends on their accuracy. Let's see some of the measuring devices we're going to use in table 2.2.

Table 2.2: Measuring devices

Parameter	Device name
Temperature	Thermocouple
Solar intensity	Solar power meter
Water	Scaled vessel

We may have to use more devices but these are must for the experiment.

III. MODELING AND ANALYSIS

Experimental Setup

In this probable setup we have glass cover, wooden box, absorber plate, fins, phase change material (PCM) etc. First, we have to build a wooden box. For glass cover we'll use 3mm thick glass; as we known earlier less thickness of glass give better performance. And the glass cover should be inclined around 30°. As latitude angle of Bangladesh is 22°. Bilal et al. [25] done an investigation on solar still using different angles. He created five different situations such as 15°, 25°, 35°, 45°, 55° and found that the better inclination for more production is 35°. For absorber plate we're going to use galvanized steel plate and we'll paint it with black color. That's because black color help it absorbs more solar radiation. And galvanizing will help steel to resist corrosion for a longer time. The area and thickness of the steel sheet will be (60×30) cm and 1 mm respectively.

Fig 3.1: Absorber plate with fins

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Here we are more interested in efficiency of the system. We can measure other parameters too but that will make our work more complicated. The efficiency of a solar still depends on productivity of that solar still, solar intensity, area of the absorber, latent heat of vaporization. Let's see formula for calculating hourly and daily thermal efficiency [14].

Hourly thermal efficiency = (Hourly production × latent heat) / (Solar radiation intensity × absorber area × time interval)

$$\text{Or, } \eta = \frac{P \times L}{I \times A \times \Delta t} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Here P is daily production, L is latent heat of water (j/kg), I is solar intensity (W/m²), A is absorber area (m²), Δt is time interval (s). Our hourly efficiency will vary because the intensity of solar radiation is not same in an entire day and also in different days. The experiment will be done in winter season; so, it will be a great challenge to cope up with cold, windy and less solar radiation condition.

V. CONCLUSION

If we manage to build our setup accurately then we're hoping that we'll be able to collect fresh potable water. To operate this, we don't need any expertise. No conventional energy, low investment, better performance makes this process more attractive. Productivity and efficiency can be shown after doing the paper.

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